

THE STRUCTURE OF TEKES AND THEIR ROLE IN SOCIAL LIFE

Ismailov Gafurjon Khasanovich

Doctoral Candidate (PhD), Bukhara State University
200100, 11 M.Ikbol Street, Bukhara, Republic of Uzbekistan
Ismoilov9191@mail.ru

Abstract: This article analyzes the social structure of tekkes, their role in religious and spiritual activity, and their influence on community life. Tekkes functioned not only as religious centers but also as institutions providing scientific, cultural, athletic, and social assistance. The article elaborates on their organizational structure, the roles of shaykhs and dervishes, as well as the responsibilities of the serving staff. It also discusses the contribution of tekkes to the development of sports, the reduction of social stratification, and the alleviation of unemployment in society.

Keywords: Tekke, Sufism, shaykh, dervish, dhikr, mausoleum, madrasa, charity, social life, religious education, historical heritage, Muslim community, legal status, international relations.

Tekkes had not only a spiritual structure but also material resources that ensured their continuous functioning. These resources included servants, teachers, and students, who together formed the core of the tekke community. At the same time, the connection between the tekke and the people was extremely important and strong. In the regions where they were established, tekkes served Islam, introduced people to the religion, and inspired love for it. In areas where Islam had only begun to spread, they made it easier for people to embrace the faith.

Thanks to the tekkes, which reached all layers of society, communication between the people and the scholars (ulama) became stronger. People gathered for evening conversations and dhikr assemblies, discussed their problems, and sought advice together. From a structural perspective, it is clear that tekkes were social institutions. Being closely connected with the people, they not only unified society but also eliminated class differences between social groups.[1]

Tekkes always managed to preserve their existence. In some regions, after the death of shaykhs whose students had either left or been sent to other tekkes, these places began to function as mausoleums. The Markaz Afandi Mausoleum serves as one of the best examples of this. In their time, tekkes were important and

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influential institutions; all levels of society—from state officials to merchants—needed their support and acted as their patrons. Because they addressed large audiences, tekkes became both a source of protection and a means of influence for states. Mosques and tekkes were mutually supportive institutions, with mosque imams and tekke shaykhs often acting together as religious leaders.

It is clear that tekkes were not only religious institutions beneficial to the public but also social centers that carried out various communal activities. Especially during the Ottoman period, there were tekkes dedicated to wrestling, archery, and sports. Founded by representatives of different athletic and craft disciplines, these tekkes served as gathering centers where people came together on specific days and at set times. As their names suggest, such tekkes were places where sports activities were conducted and encouraged in society.

Thus, tekkes were not limited to providing religious education but were broad social institutions serving multiple purposes. They can even be viewed as organizations that laid the foundation for the formation of modern sports academies. The sports activities organized by tekkes attracted wide recognition and public attention. One of their most important characteristics was that every activity offered was carried out in accordance with the Sunnah and within religious boundaries. Wrestling, in particular, has long been one of the symbolic sports of our society. Beyond being a simple athletic discipline, it deserves recognition as an activity reflecting both religious and social values.[2]

Wrestling was one of the traditional athletic activities of the Turkic peoples even before the advent of Islam. After the adoption of Islam, it retained its importance and continued to develop. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) always supported sports that promoted physical development and strength. Because wrestling was one of such sports, it continued within the framework of Islam as the “sport of the Prophet.” The Prophet’s cousin, Hazrat Hamza, was known as the greatest of wrestlers. Tekkes played an active role in the development of this important sport.

For the upper strata of society — the scholarly and noble classes — there were private opportunities and places to practice wrestling, while for ordinary people, this role was fulfilled by the sports tekkes established by the sultans. Especially during the Ottoman period, wrestling tekkes were found in many cities and provinces, particularly in Bursa, Konya, Edirne, and Istanbul.[3]

Archery (shooting with a bow) was one of the sports recommended by the Sunnah. The Prophet (peace be upon him) advised and encouraged his companions

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to practice it. This sport not only strengthened the body but also served as an important means of defense during wars. The Ottoman Empire, as in every field, excelled in archery and attached great importance to this sport, which was part of the Prophet's Sunnah. Among the companions, Sa'd ibn Abi Waqqas (may Allah be pleased with him) was famous for his mastery of archery and was one of those promised Paradise. He especially attracted the Prophet's attention during the Battle of Uhud, earning his praise for his skill and bravery.

Archery later developed not only as a method of military defense but also as a sport for enthusiasts. Although in the Ottoman Empire archery ceased to serve as a primary military tool after the nineteenth century, archery tekkes (lodges for bowmen) continued to exist both during that period and in later times.

Tekkes also fulfilled the function of providing employment within society. They created job opportunities for many people. To meet daily needs, tekkes hired salaried workers who performed various duties ranging from educational tasks to maintenance and cleaning. The duties and responsibilities of these workers were assigned by the murshids.

According to their general structure, the staff in tekkes were divided into two categories:

- Educational personnel
- Service personnel

The highest religious authority in the tekke was the shaykh. Three types of individuals could hold the rank of shaykh: scholars (ulama), Sufi masters (mutasavvifs), and tribal shaykhs. The teaching shaykhs within the tekke were required to be exemplary figures, possessing deep knowledge and strong moral qualities.

Following the shaykhs, the most important religious figures in the tekke hierarchy were the dervishes. The word dervish literally means "poor" or "humble." While the shaykhs served as mentors, the dervishes were their disciples. There were three types of dervishes:

- Resident dervishes – those who lived permanently in the tekke.
- Visiting dervishes – those who came and went daily.

Stationed dervishes – those who resided in a specific section of the tekke and continued their spiritual journey there.

After completing their education, dervishes continued to serve either in their own tekke or in another as teachers, Sufis (mutasavvifs), or murshids.

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In addition to shaykhs and dervishes, tekkes also employed other religious staff who performed specific duties:

- Turbadar – a servant responsible for cleaning and maintaining the tekke’s mausoleums.
- Juzkhon – a person who recited the Holy Qur’an.
- Mavludkhon – a person who recited mawlid (poems in praise of the Prophet) during important nights and religious ceremonies.
- Zakir – a reciter who sang spiritual hymns during dhikr ceremonies, uplifting the spiritual enthusiasm of the dervishes.
- Imam and muezzin – those who performed religious services in the mosques associated with the tekke.
- Duogo’y – a person who offered prayers at the conclusion of conversations and dhikr gatherings.

These religious staff members played an important role in the religious, social, and spiritual life of the tekkes.

Tekkes were not limited to employing only religious personnel; they also had servants responsible for daily operations such as receiving guests, preparing food for travelers and the needy, and maintaining the facilities. One of the most important of these servants was the tabbakh (cook). The tabbakh—responsible for preparing meals—was considered an essential part of every tekke.

In addition, there were farroshees (cleaners) who maintained cleanliness in the tekkes. They swept and cleaned both the interior and exterior areas, ensuring that the premises remained neat and orderly.

Several other servants assisted the tabbakhs in their work, including:

- Bulokchi – responsible for washing dishes and utensils.
- Eshikbon – in charge of supervising entries and exits at the tekke.
- Halvochi – responsible for preparing sweets and special dishes.

Furthermore, qayyums and bawwabs handled the arrangement and cleanliness of the dhikr and conversation rooms, performing important maintenance duties within the tekke.

Based on this information, it can be concluded that tekkes functioned not only as religious and educational centers but also as institutions that provided employment, hospitality, dining services, and social assistance to the community.

The existence of tekkes dedicated to various types of sports, as well as the information about the individuals who served in them and their duties, clearly demonstrates the significance and role of tekkes in social life. Tekkes held an

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important place in the eyes of both the state and the people, and because they fulfilled multiple functions, they continued to operate for many years. Owing to their contributions in religious, political, economic, and even military fields, they were officially recognized and supported by the government.

Especially during the Ottoman period, tekkes were exempted from taxes for extended periods. In certain times, tekke employees and shaykhs even received salaries from the state. From a social perspective, being associated with a tekke always brought both religious and economic advantages to individuals.[4]

It can therefore be concluded that states which provided material support to tekkes were at times also in need of their protection. Tekkes located in border regions as well as those in central cities played vital roles in maintaining peace among the people, preserving order, and fostering social unity. Every ruler who sought to establish good governance understood that tekkes should not be opposed but rather supported, and thus granted them due attention and specific responsibilities. In particular, tekkes situated along borders were also responsible for ensuring the security of those areas.

Serving as bridges between the state and the people, tekkes in a sense laid the foundations for the earliest forms of labor and professional unions.[5]

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